

Impact of atmospheric boundary layer profiling

Chapter: Urban environments

Document version	1
Version date	17/05/2024
PROBE deliverables	1.5
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1. Introduction

There is a trend in recent decades that urban population grows significantly and the process of urbanisation increasing enormously which have posed several challenges for decision-makers in cities and metropolitan areas. The vulnerability of cities due to the increasing number of extreme weather events and the effects of climate change are placing additional significant burdens on urban management organisations and agencies and eventually have a severe impact on the well-being of the population. In recent years meteorological agencies can predict quite precisely local extreme weather events a few hours earlier before they occur, but it highly depends on the monitoring system, the network and the density of stations. However, the network of deployed stations is only affordable in big cities or capitals. EU level initiatives are also dedicated to support urban development, among others. [COPERNICUS Services](#) have a wide range of thematic fields to promote human well-being and safety and economic growth. It provides information drawn from satellite Earth Observation and in-situ data. For strategic planning the topic Land is the most commonly used through the CORINE database for all of Europe and there are high spatial resolution databases for selected big cities and metropolitan areas. The great advantage of these databases is that they are free of charge, however, the temporal resolution is still low, which can hardly improve at European level, when high resolution datasets are required for both temporally and spatially. Local air quality and the dispersion of pollutants in an industrial area or in case of point-source emitters cannot be monitored with these datasets.

Global initiatives like The Covenant of Mayors, for example, are seeking solutions to make cities more resilient through adaptation measures. To make appropriate roadmap to implement these measures the planning sound based on data collection, modelling and simulations. Decision-makers usually have a wide range of tools at their disposal to address these challenges and develop resilience, but a better understanding of the microclimate and the environment of the settlement, as well the circumstances and sequences of extreme weather events could be essential to make informed decisions and choose proper development paths. The development of Urban Heat Islands or the propagation of air pollutants requires targeted measures.

In the framework of PROBE COST Action selected applications related to the study of atmospheric boundary layer are introduced below, which aim the deeper understanding of lower atmospheric processes over urban areas and can also play a decision support role through data gathering, model building and monitoring. Each application has its own specifications, and the below list is non-exhaustive. Although, to select the most appropriate ones for the given case, the support of an urban planner or similar expertise may be needed.

2. Low-level jet

The Low-Level Jet (LLJ) and the Urban Heat Island (UHI) are common nocturnal phenomena in the atmospheric boundary layer. While the canopy layer UHI has been studied extensively, interactions of the LLJ and the urban atmosphere in general (and the UHI in particular) have received less attention. In the framework of the PANAME initiative in the Paris region, continuous measurements of wind speed and vertical velocity profiles were recorded with two Doppler Wind Lidars (DWL) - for the first time allowing for a detailed investigation of the summertime LLJ characteristics in the region (Cespedes et al. 2024). Jets are detected for 70% of the examined nights, often simultaneously at an urban (QUALAIR-SU) and a suburban site (SIRTA) highlighting the LLJ regional spatial extent. Emerging at around sunset, the mean LLJ duration is ~10 h, the mean wind speed is ~9 m/s, and the average core height is 400 m above the city. For many jets, results show signatures in the temporal evolution that indicate that the inertial oscillation mechanism plays a role in the jet development: a clockwise veering of the wind direction and a rapid acceleration followed by a slower deceleration. The LLJ core wind

shear induces variance in the vertical velocity (σ_2w) above the urban canopy layer. It is shown that σ_2w is a powerful indicator for the air temperature spatial contrasts as UHI intensity decreases exponentially with increasing σ_2w and strong values only occur when σ_2w is very weak. This study demonstrates how DWL observations in cities provide valuable insights into near-surface processes relevant to human and environmental health.

Figure 1. Mean profiles of a) horizontal wind speed and b) median profiles of vertical velocity variance σ_2w . The solid lines represent the composite profile with all 30-min profiles detected as LLJ, and the shadows denote $1\pm\text{std}$. Each panel presents the respective profiles for each σ_2w class: red is low σ_2w , orange is moderate, and blue is strong σ_2w . Cespedes et al (2024)

Figure 2. Relations between the nocturnal average of ΔUHI intensity for all cloud-free nights in the study period and a) 10m agl wind speed at Melun, the rural reference site. The dots are coloured by the surface wind direction at Melun. The dashed black curve is the best fit for the data: $y = 3((x-1.2)-0.5)$, and it follows the empirical relationship described by Oke (1973) b) the σ_2w at 238 m agl, dots are coloured by the LLJ core height above the ground surface. The dashed black curve represents the best non-linear fit found for the data collected in the Paris region and determines ΔUHI intensity with QUALAIR-SU data. The dotted black curve represents the same but using data collected by a surface-based station installed at Boulevard de Capucines for a shorter period. Both curves represent the equation: $y = -1.39 \log(x)+0.84$. The background shading indicates the LLJ classes described in Section 3.2. In all subplots, dots, and triangles represent nights with and without LLJ events, respectively. Cespedes et al (2024)

3. Wind profiling for wind climatology

Wind climatology, including turbulence statistics, is required for any microscale dispersion study. Such studies are concerned, for example, with local emergency plans in the vicinity of potential hazards (ammonia tanks, nuclear medicine centres, etc.), ventilation of traffic pollution from street canyons, wind and thermal comfort in cities, etc. Microscale dispersion studies are solved by physical models (wind tunnel tests) or micrometeorological numerical models. Both methods are based on very fine resolution within the area of interest, and both are limited by the maximum area that can be covered with the given resolution. The dispersion characteristics of any pollutant are very sensitive to the level of flow turbulence. Complex urban topography can produce a wide range of turbulent features (e.g. cavity vortices, wake formation, irregular flow separation, flapping winds). The flow within the urban canopy is driven by the flow above the canopy, which in turn is influenced by the upwind surface topography. Remote sensing instruments such as Doppler Wind Lidars (DWL) can monitor the flow just above the urban canopy at a suitable frequency and resolution to capture the characteristics of the turbulent flow and provide input to the micrometeorological models.

Processing the measured data into a wind climatology is a challenging task. The turbulence characteristics such as turbulence intensity, shear stresses, integral length scales and energy spectra require time series of sufficient length and detrending. The difficulties in processing DWL data are described in this report: KELLNE-VM-W1.

4. Urban boundary layer dynamics

The spatial distribution of heat, moisture and atmospheric pollutants is of course largely affected by heterogeneity of the respective sources, but also transport mechanisms in the atmospheric boundary layer play an important role. To better understand the relative importance of mixing, dilution, entrainment and advection in the urban atmosphere, it is vital to quantify the effectiveness of vertical motions in the atmosphere, i.e. the atmospheric stability. It is known that the added heat and surface roughness over cities enhance thermal buoyancy and momentum transport, whereby destabilising the near-surface atmosphere. While stable stratification over rural surfaces is the norm at night, the boundary layer over dense urban surfaces is more likely to remain neutral or even slightly unstable even at night. During the day, the height of the convective boundary layer can be significantly greater due to the stronger vertical motion (see Figure 3). However, to date, continuous monitoring of these effects is rare and multiple variables need to be observed simultaneously to be able to quantify the thermal stratification of the atmosphere on the one hand and the horizontal and vertical motion on the other. Turbulence observations can provide added value as they can be interpreted as a direct assessment of mixing processes.

Figure 3: Seasonal diurnal pattern of mixed layer height (MLH) relative to time since sunrise detected at a central urban and a sub-urban location in the megacity of Paris, France, during the period Dec 2016 – Oct 2019. (top row) solid line is the median MLH with shading the inter-quartile range, (middle row) median and inter-quartile range of instantaneous differences, and (bottom row) number of samples. Cimini et al. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42865-020-00003-8>

In the context of the PANAME (<https://paname.aeris-data.fr/>) initiative in the Paris region (France), effective project collaborations enabled the design of a detailed ground-based remote sensing monitoring network. Three supersites were installed along a suburban-urban transect, each equipped with microwave radiometers (MWR) to monitor temperature profiles, Doppler wind lidars to record vertical profiles of wind and turbulence, as well as automatic lidars and ceilometers (ALC) that track aerosol backscatter and cloud base height.

On-going activities have already highlighted the benefit brought by instrumental synergy to better understand the link between urban heat islands and the atmospheric dynamics.

5. Urban air quality

Aerosol regional transport impact on AQ: examples of the Po Valley

The operational use of active remote sensing from ALC systems has been a key tool to reveal and quantify the export of pollutants from the Po Valley to surrounding areas. A recent study performed using data collected in the northwestern Italian Alps showed that, mostly due to thermal winds producing typical mountain-valley daily circulations, Po Valley pollution markedly affects PM-related AQ in the surrounding ‘pristine’ mountain environments, namely the Alpine and pre-Alpine areas (Diemmoz et al., 2019a,b). The phenomenon was first observed by lidar observations performed at the EC-JRC in Ispra (VA), about 60 km northwest of the Milan metropolitan area (Barnaba et al., 2010), and has been recently thoroughly investigated by means of continuous (24/7) data from the ALICEnet ALC systems at Milan and Aosta, respectively within and at the NW border of the Po Valley (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Locations of the two ALICEnet ALC systems at Aosta and Milan in the Po Valley, Italy.

The local EPA (Arpa Valle d’Aosta) is operating an ALC at Aosta to complement standard AQMN measurements. Since its first deployment, this system captures recurrent aerosol layers arriving in the afternoon and persisting during the night, characterising the aerosol vertical profiles up to 4 km altitude. It has been demonstrated (Diemmoz et al., 2019a,b) that this is a regional phenomenon mostly driven by mountain-valley breezes bringing polluted aerosol plumes from the Po Valley to the surrounding mountainous regions (Aosta, Figure 5a). Simultaneous ALC observations performed at the Po Valley pollution hotspot of Milan show how this phenomenon produces the reverse effect in the centre of the valley, i.e., a removal or ‘cleaning’ of PM in the afternoon hours (Figure 5b).

(a) ALICenet lev2 profiles in Aosta

(b) ALICenet lev2 profiles in Milan

Figure 5: Continuous aerosol profiles (aerosol scattering ratio, ALICenet Level 2 profiles) from ALC at Aosta and Milan in the period 25-31 August 2015. Adapted from Diemoz et al. 2019a.

Overall, the operational use of ALC systems with support of modelling tools and in-situ AQ observations revealed a major impact of such a regular, ‘aerosol tide’ on the trans-regional AQ. Based on 3 years of continuous measurements it was shown that in relatively ‘clean’ environments such as the Aosta Alpine area, this regular import from the Po Valley leads to a significant increase of PM10 concentrations (up-to a factor of 3.5). These aerosol-rich layers can extend to a depth of up to 4 km and are observed with a frequency of 50% of the days overall but occur with a frequency of up to 93% when only days with easterly winds (i.e., outflow from the Po Basin) are considered and 100% if air mass residence time over the Po Valley is > 10 h (Figure 5).

Figure 6: Contingency table based on 3-years (2015-2017) of continuous data showing occurrences of detection of the aerosol layer by the ALC in relation to a) wind direction and b) residence time of air masses in the Po Valley (evaluated by 48 h back-trajectories). The orange (blue) boxes represent cases when the aerosol layer is (is not) present. Adapted from Diemoz et al. 2019b.

Coupling of ALC observations with Positive Matrix Factorisation (PMF) of chemical properties at surface level revealed that particles advected from the Po Valley to the northwestern Alps are mostly of

secondary origin and mainly composed of nitrates, sulphates, and ammonium. An important organic component was also detected in the warm season (Diemoz et al., 2019b).

The operational deployment of ALC remote sensing systems also allows better understanding and interpretation of particular long- and short-range transport phenomena impacting PM-related AQ, including (but not limited to) desert dust or fire plumes. An example of this capability is provided below (Figure xx): a particular case of rapid and intense deterioration of AQ in the urban area of Milan in April 2020. The episode was due to an extended (about 100 km) gust front originating from the cold and intense Bora wind from East (Figure xx), raising and transporting farming residuals across the entire Po Valley. In fact, the episode was preceded by a particularly dry period, an anomalous condition affecting most of Europe in that month. Note that a quite similar event was recorded at the same sites also in April 2022.

Figure 7: a) Central Milan camera showing the rapid decrease of visibility/increase of PM on 14/07/2020 (from top to bottom: pictures at 16:08, 16:15, 16:20, 16:25 UTC), b) Po Valley satellite true colour image, and c) 10 m wind speed and direction simulated by WRF over North Italy (14/07/2020 17:00 UTC, courtesy of Stefano Federico CNR/ISAC) illustrating the extension of the gust and wind fronts generating this effect.

The corresponding aerosol mass concentration profiles derived from ALC observations at Milan (Figure 8a) nicely capture the timing of the plume arrival and show the vertical extent of the particle-rich layer associated with the episode. The plume continued to travel westward and was detected by the ALC at Aosta (Figure 8b) four hours later, indicating a horizontal wind speed of more than 12 m/s.

Figure 8: ALICENet aerosol mass profiles in a) Milan and b) Aosta, 14 April 2020.

6. References

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